

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Acceptance Note for **TEBT-2025-0015**

Submission information table

Submission Title	An update on micro- and nanoplastics in foods from plastic food contact articles: Protocol for a systematic evidence map
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0015
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	1 editor, 3 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Method (Protocol for Planned Study) ▾
Preregistration Category	Category 1 (Open Lab Notebook Preregistration) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17151839
Report Number	3 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note ▾
Evaluation Date	15 Feb 2026
Use of AI in evaluation	DataSeer.ai was used to check the consistency of the data availability statements in the manuscript with journal policies.
Recommendation	Accept with In-Principle Acceptance ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript presents a protocol for a complex and challenging mapping of the literature about the migration of micro- and nanoplastic particles from food contact materials into foodstuffs. This is a significant update of prior work by the authors, will be a useful resource for other researchers, and forms the basis for follow-up work to assess microplastic exposures from food contact materials.

Comments from editorial triage related to ensuring the study goals were aligned with a mapping methodology; reconsidering the structure and processes for search, screening, study appraisal, and data analysis in the study, with regard to study goals and meeting the anticipated needs of the target users of the evidence map; and revision of the coding strategy and some other detailed elements of the methodology to ensure the evidence map can deliver the planned objectives.

The authors comprehensively revised their manuscript, which was then peer-reviewed. Two of the three reviewers responded positively to the manuscript. One reviewer did not, but they did not explain their view that the proposed methodology is not a sufficient update of the previous work.

Since the editor and two reviewers view the manuscript as a significant update on a prior approach, and that peer-review and publication of the protocol is an important part of ensuring the utility and validity of the update to the evidence, we recommended minor revisions instead of following the dissenting reviewer's recommendation to reject the manuscript.

The authors completed these minor revisions, and we are therefore pleased to accept the manuscript for publication. Finally we note that, as a journal, and notwithstanding the authors' arguments about ensuring appropriate use, we would prefer if the dataset from this work could ultimately be made publicly available by default rather than available on request.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript was accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 1 round of editorial evaluation and 1 round of peer-review evaluation. The evaluation reports for the manuscript can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333133>. Preprint versions of the manuscript and author responses to comments in the evaluation reports can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17151839>.

In the editor's opinion, this protocol is a [Category 1 preregistration](#), because enough of the data that will be used to answer the research question has been previously observed or analysed by the authors that it would allow them to predict or anticipate the findings of the planned study, but the authors have not yet analysed the data according to the methods they present in their protocol.

According to our Registered Reports policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods and provide a defensible and evidence-based interpretation of their results.